

ExtremeEarth
H2020 - 825258

Deliverable

D3.1

**Transforming big geospatial data into RDF and
evaluation**

Georgios Mandilaras

and

**Dimitris Bilidas, Theofilos Ioannidis and Manolis
Koubarakis**

June 27, 2019

Status: Final
Scheduled Delivery Date: 30/06/2019

Executive Summary

The deliverable D3.1 is part of WP3 which objective is to develop a set of tools for querying, integration and extreme analytics for the big information and knowledge that will be mined from Copernicus data and other auxiliary data sources using the techniques of WP2. This information and knowledge will be encoded as linked geospatial data and will be integrated with other open linked data sources to be demonstrated in the two use cases of ExtremeEarth. The deliverable D3.1 concerns the transformation of big geospatial data into RDF which is implemented using GeoTriples. GeoTriples is an open source tool developed by UoA and supports the automatic transformation of geospatial data from various formats (e.g., shapefiles) into RDF using Semantic Web standards. For the purpose of ExtremeEarth, we have re-engineered GeoTriples using the Hops data platform, enabling users to perform transformation of big geospatial data into RDF at the extreme scales of the Copernicus paradigm.

Document Information

Contract Number	H2020 - 825258	Acronym	ExtremeEarth
Full title	ExtremeEarth		
Project URL	http://earthanalytics.eu/		
EU Project Officer	Riku Leppänen		

Deliverable	Number	D3.1	Name	Transforming big geospatial data into RDF and evaluation	
Task	Number	T3.1	Name	Transformation of big geospatial data into RDF	
Work package	Number			WP3	
Date of delivery	Contract	30/06/2019		Actual	30/06/2019
Status	Draft <input type="checkbox"/> Final <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				
Nature	Prototype <input type="checkbox"/> Report <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				
Distribution Type	Public <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Restricted <input type="checkbox"/>				
Responsible Partner	UoA				
QA Partner	NCSR-D				
Contact Person	Prof. Manolis Koubarakis				
	Email	koubarak@di.uoa.gr	Phone	+302107275213	Fax +302107275214

Project Information

This document is part of a research project funded by the IST Programme of the Commission of the European Communities as project number H2020-825258. The beneficiaries in this project are the following:

Partner	Acronym	Contact
National and Kapodistrian University of Athens Department of Informatics and Telecommunications (Coordinator)	UoA 	Prof. Manolis Koubarakis National and Kapodistrian University of Athens Dept. of Informatics and Telecommunications Panepistimiopolis, Ilissia, GR-15784 Athens, Greece Email: (koubarak@di.uoa.gr) Tel: +30 210 7275213, Fax: +30 210 7275214
VISTA Geowissenschaftliche Fernerkundung GmbH	VISTA 	Heike Bach Email: (bach@vista-geo.de)
The Arctic University of Norway Department of Physics and Technology	UiT 	Torbjørn Eltoft Email: (torbjorn.eltoft@uit.no)
University of Trento Department of Information Engineering and Computer Science	UNITN 	Lorenzo Bruzzone Email: (lorenzo.bruzzone@unitn.it)
Royal Institute of Technology	KTH 	Seif Haridi Email: (haridi@kth.se)
National Center for Scientific Research - Demokritos	NCSR-D 	Vangelis Karkaletsis Email: (vangelis@iit.demokritos.gr)
Deutsches Zentrum für Luft-und Raumfahrt e. V.	DLR 	Corneliu Octavian Dumitru Email: (corneliu.dumitru@dlr.de)
Polar View Earth Observation Ltd.	PolarView 	David Arthurs Email: (david.arthurs@polarview.org)
METEOROLOGISK INSTITUTT	METNO 	Nick Hughes Email: (nick.hughes@met.no)
Logical Clocks AB	LC 	Jim Dowling Email: (jim@logicalclocks.com)
United Kingdom Research and Innovation - British Antarctic Survey	UKRI-BAS 	Andrew Fleming Email: (ahf@bas.ac.uk)

Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	Background	3
2.1	stSPARQL and GeoSPARQL	3
2.2	Direct Mapping of Relational Data to RDF	3
2.3	The Mapping Language R2RML	3
2.4	The Mapping Language RML	4
2.5	Apache Spark	5
2.5.1	Support of spatial formats	6
2.6	Hops	7
2.6.1	HopsFS	7
2.6.2	HopsYARN	8
2.6.3	Hopswork	8
3	The Tool GeoTriples	9
3.1	System Architecture	9
3.2	Implementation Details	9
3.3	Automatic generation of R2RML and RML mappings	10
3.4	Processing of R2RML and RML Mappings	11
4	Transformation of Big Geospatial Data	15
4.1	Description	15
4.2	Evaluation	17
4.2.1	CSV	17
4.2.2	GeoJSON	19
4.2.3	ESRI Shapefile	20
4.2.4	Execution in HDFS	23
5	Summary	25

List of Figures

2.1	R2RML and RML overview. White boxes denote R2RML components, green boxes denote R2RML components extended by RML and orange boxes denote RML specific components. Arrows with white arrowhead denote subclasses, arrows with dashed line and white arrowhead denote the different types of TermMap and simple lines denote associations.	6
2.2	Hopswork Architecture	7
3.1	The system architecture of GeoTriples	10
4.1	Performance of GeoTriples-Spark for CSV datasets of different sizes	18
4.2	HDFS I/O triggered by GeoTriples-Spark during the transformation of 2TB CSV data	19
4.3	Performance of GeoTriples-Spark for GeoJSON datasets of different sizes	20
4.4	Performance of GeoTriples-Spark for reading multiple ESRI Shapefiles	22
4.5	Performance of GeoTriples-Spark against Shapefile datasets	22
4.6	HDFS I/O triggered by GeoTriples-Spark during the transformation of 1TB of geospatial data loaded by ESRI Shapefiles	23
4.7	Execution of GeoTriples-Spark in a pseudo-distributed HDFS cluster	24

List of Tables

4.1	CSV Datasets	18
4.2	CSV Tests	18
4.3	GeoJSON Datasets	20
4.4	GeoJSON Tests	20
4.5	ESRI Shapefiles Datasets	21
4.6	ESRI Shapefiles Datasets	21
4.7	Performance of GeoTriples-Spark for reading multiple ESRI Shapefiles	21
4.8	ESRI Shapefile Tests	22

1. Introduction

In this deliverable we present the transformation of big geospatial data into linked open data. Its goal is to open up TEPs and DIASs by publishing the information and knowledge of their data into linked data. This will allow the interlinking with non-EO data and will enable not only EO experts but also myriad software developers to gain from this information by integrating EO data in their application.

In the last few years, the area of linked geospatial data has received attention as researchers and practitioners have started tapping the wealth of existing geospatial information and making it available on the Web [KBP⁺17, KKK⁺12a]. As a result, the linked open data (LOD) cloud has been slowly populated with geospatial data. For example, Great Britain's national mapping agency, Ordnance Survey¹, has been the first national mapping agency that has made various kinds of geospatial data from Great Britain available as linked open data. Similarly, projects TELEIOS², LEO³, MELODIES⁴ and Copernicus App Lab⁵, in which our research groups participated, published a number of geospatial datasets that are Earth observation products e.g., CORINE Land Cover and Urban Atlas⁶. Also, the Spatial Data on the Web working group created jointly by the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) and the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) has produced in 2017 five relevant working notes on best practices, use cases and requirements, Earth observation data, spatio-temporal data cubes and coverages as linked data.

Geospatial data can come in vector or raster form and are usually accompanied by metadata. Vector data, available in formats such as ESRI shapefiles, KML, and GeoJSON documents, can be accessed either directly or via Web Services such as the OGC Web Feature Service or the query language of a geospatial DBMS. Raster data, available in formats such as GeoTIFF, Network Common Data Form (netCDF) and Hierarchical Data Format (HDF), can be accessed either directly or via Web Services such as the OGC Web Coverage Processing Service (WCS) or the query language of an array DBMS, e.g., rasdaman or MonetDB/SciQL. Metadata about geospatial data are encoded in various formats ranging from custom XML schemas to domain-specific standards like the OGC GML Application Schema for EO products and the OGC Metadata Profile of Observations and Measurements. Automating the process of transforming input geospatial data to linked data has only been addressed by few works so far[ALH09, CV13, KKG⁺14, dLSV⁺10, PAGA14].

In this work, we present the tool GeoTriples⁷ that performs the transformation of geospatial data from various formats into RDF graphs. Furthermore, the new, parallelized version of GeoTriples that work on top of Hops and Apache Spark. Using this new system, we will be able to transform geospatial data from their native formats into RDF at the extreme scales of the Copernicus context.

GeoTriples is a semi-automated tool that enables the automatic transformation of geospatial data into RDF graphs using state of the art vocabularies like GeoSPARQL[geo12], but at the same time, it is not tightly coupled to a specific vocabulary. The transformation process comprises three steps. First, GeoTriples generates automatically extended R2RML or RML mappings for transforming data that reside in spatially-enabled databases or raw files into RDF. As an optional second step, the user may revise these mappings according to her needs e.g., to utilize a different vocabulary. Finally, GeoTriples processes these mappings and produces an RDF graph. The input formats supported by GeoTriples are spatially-enabled relational databases (PostGIS and MonetDB), ESRI shapefiles, XML documents following a given schema (hence GML documents as well), KML documents, JSON and GeoJSON documents and CSV documents. The distributed version supports the conversion of ESRI Shapefiles, CSV files and GeoJSON documents.

¹<https://www.ordnancesurvey.co.uk/>

²<http://www.earthobservatory.eu/>

³<http://www.linkedeodata.eu/>

⁴<https://www.melodiesproject.eu/>

⁵<https://www.app-lab.eu/>

⁶<http://kr.di.uoa.gr/#datasets>

⁷<http://geotriples.di.uoa.gr/>

The rest of this deliverable is organized as follows. Section 2 discusses the necessary background needed for understanding the process of transformation. Section 3 gives detailed information about the tool GeoTriples. In Section 4 we present the extension of GeoTriples to support the transformation of big geospatial data and the evaluation. Last, in Section 5 we summarize.

2. Background

In this section, we present methodologies and tools necessary for understanding the overall execution of GeoTriples and the transformation of big geospatial data into RDF graphs. As regards mapping, we will discuss two state-of-the-art approaches, direct mapping and R2RML and a proposal for mapping heterogeneous data into RDF, the mapping language RML. Furthermore, we present the Hops and the Apache Spark frameworks which are fundamental to the extension of GeoTriples to support the transformation of big geospatial data.

2.1 stSPARQL and GeoSPARQL

Much work has been done recently on extending RDF to represent and query geospatial information. The most mature results are the data model stRDF and the query language stSPARQL [KKK12b, BSK13] and the OGC standard GeoSPARQL [geo12]. These data models and query languages have been implemented in many geospatial triple stores including Strabon [KKK12b], GraphDB¹, Oracle Spatial and Graph², etc.

stRDF is an extension of the W3C standard RDF that allows the representation of geospatial data that changes over time [KKK12b, BSK13]. stRDF is accompanied by stSPARQL, an extension of the query language SPARQL 1.1 for querying and updating stRDF data. stRDF and stSPARQL use OGC standards WKT and GML for a serialized representation of temporal and geospatial data. GeoSPARQL is an OGC standard for the representation and querying of linked geospatial data. GeoSPARQL defines much of what is required for such a query language by providing a vocabulary (classes, properties, and functions) that can be used in geospatial RDF graphs and SPARQL queries.

2.2 Direct Mapping of Relational Data to RDF

A straightforward mechanism for mapping relational data into RDF is the direct mapping approach that became a W3C recommendation in 2012 [BAPS12]. In this approach tables in a relational database are mapped to classes defined by an RDFS vocabulary, while attributes of each table are mapped to RDF properties that represent the relation between subject and object resources. Identifiers, class names, properties, and instances are generated automatically following the respective labels of the input data. For example, given the table Address, the class <Address> is generated, and every tuple is represented by a resource that becomes an instance of this class. The generation of RDF data is dictated by the schema of the relational database. This mechanism was initially defined in [BL], and [Ste06] is an implementation of it.

2.3 The Mapping Language R2RML

A language for expressing customized mappings from relational databases to RDF graphs is the R2RML mapping language that became W3C recommendation in 2012 [DSC12]. R2RML mappings provide the user with the ability to express the desired transformation of existing relational data into the RDF data model, following a structure and a target vocabulary that is chosen by him or her. R2RML mappings refer to logical tables to retrieve data from an input database. A

¹<https://ontotext.com/products/graphdb/>

²<http://www.oracle.com/technetwork/database/options/spatialandgraph/overview/index.html>

logical table can be a relational table, an SQL view that exists in a database or an SQL SELECT query. A triples map is defined for each logical table that will be exported into RDF. A triples map is a rule that defines how each tuple of the logical table will be mapped to a set of RDF triples. A triples map consists of a subject map and one or more predicate-object maps. A subject map is a rule that defines how to generate the URI that will be the subject of each generated RDF triple. Usually, the primary key of the relation is used for this purpose. A predicate-object map consists of predicate maps and object maps. A predicate map defines the RDF property to be used to relate the subject and the object of the generated triple. An object map defines how to generate the object of the triple, the value of which originates from the value of the attribute of the specified logical table. Subject maps, predicate maps and object maps are term maps. A term map is a function that generates an RDF term from a logical table. Three types of term maps are defined: constant-valued term maps that always generate the same RDF term, column-valued term maps that generate RDF terms from an attribute of the input relation, and template-valued term maps that generate RDF terms according to a template. R2RML defines the vocabulary to express foreign key relationships among logical tables. For this purpose, a join condition is introduced for defining the column name of the child table and the column name of the parent table. Figure 2.1a presents an overview of R2RML. R2RML is not limited to mapping relational tables to RDFS classes and relational attributes to data properties. R2RML has several other features that are presented below:

- *Ad-hoc SQL result sets*: This feature is useful in cases where the user wants to apply some transformations (e.g., syntactic modifications) or apply aggregate functions on the input data.
- *Templates*: Using the `rr:template` property, one can specify the format of a resource that will be used as a subject or an object of a triple using a string template. For example, consider the relational table `Employee(id,name,surname,salary)`. The subject of the generated resource could use the primary key `id` of the table to form a resource URI template `"http://example.com/Employee/id/"` to generate automatically resources of the form `<http://example.com/Employee/1/>`, `<http://example.com/Employee/2/>`, etc.
- *Linking two tables*: Most RDF datasets do not use only data properties (properties for which the value is a data literal), but also object properties (properties for which the value is an individual) to assert relations between resources. As a result, an R2RML mapping can take into account foreign key constraints that may exist in the underlying relational database to make such assertions.
- *Named Graphs*: Named graphs are a key concept of RDF that allows the identification of an RDF graph using a URI. As a result, contextual information like provenance information can be naturally expressed in RDF. R2RML allows a user to customize a subject map so that produced triples can belong to the default graph or any other named graph.

2.4 The Mapping Language RML

The RDF Mapping language (RML) [DVSC⁺14, DKF⁺15] is a recently proposed generic mapping language which can express rules that map data with heterogeneous structures and serializations to RDF graphs. RML is defined as a superset of R2RML and allows the expression of rules that map relational and semi-structured data (e.g., XML, JSON) into RDF graphs. The main feature of RML is that it provides the vocabulary for defining a generic data source and the iterator pattern over the input data. Note that R2RML does not define explicitly an iterator pattern over the input data since a per row iteration is implied. In contrast, RML allows the user to explicitly define an iterator that defines how the source data should be accessed. For example, an XPath expression can be defined as an iterator over an XML document, a JSONPath expression can be defined as an iterator over a JSON document and an SQL query can be defined as an iterator

over a relational database. Figure 2.1b presents an overview of RML. RML extensions to R2RML. RML has redefined all classes and properties defined in R2RML that are strictly coupled to the relational model as follows:

- The concept of logical table has been replaced by the concept of logical source which is a more generic concept that covers many kinds of input data sources. A logical source contains all necessary properties for accessing a data source and iterating over it. Similarly, the concept of table has been replaced by the more general concept of source which is a pointer to a dataset.
- The concept of iterator is a new concept that instructs a processor on how to access data from a logical source. The iterator is accompanied by a `referenceFormulation` property that specifies the query language that is being used by it. For example, for transforming an XML document into RDF, we can set the `referenceFormulation` to be the XPath language and the iterator to be the XPath query itself. Currently, the following reference formulations are defined: `rr:sqlQuery` , `ql:CSV` , `ql:XPath` , `ql:CSS3` and `ql:JSONPath`.
- The `column` property has been replaced by the more general reference property. This property is used to point to the data that is being returned by the iterator.

2.5 Apache Spark

Apache Spark³[MZ10] is an open-source, distributed, general-purpose, cluster-computing framework. It was developed by the AMP lab of UC Berkeley⁴ and it was later donated to the Apache Software Foundation⁵ which has been maintaining it ever since. Spark provides ease of use APIs for many programming languages like Java, Scala, and Python and also powers a stack of libraries including SQL, DataFrames, and Datasets, MLlib for machine learning, GraphX for graph processing, and Spark Streaming. It is able to access diverse data sources including HDFS and can be run in a cluster or in a standalone mode.

Spark uses a master/worker architecture. There is a Driver that talks to a single coordinator called Master which manages Workers in which Executors run. A Spark Driver (aka an application's driver process) is a JVM process that hosts the SparkContext for a Spark application and it is the master node. It is responsible to split the job into Tasks, to schedule them to run on Executors and to coordinate the overall execution. Executors run in different JVM processes and they are distributed agents that execute the tasks in parallel (or sequentially).

At the core of Apache Spark is the notion of data abstraction as a distributed collection of objects. This data abstraction, called Resilient Distributed Dataset (RDD) [MZ12], allows users to write programs that transform these distributed datasets. RDDs are an immutable distributed collection of elements of the data that can be stored in memory or disk across a cluster of machines. The data is partitioned across machines in the cluster, which can be operated in parallel using a high-level API that offers transformations and actions. Transformations are functions that take an RDD as input and produce one or multiple RDDs as output. They do not change the input RDD since RDDs are immutable, but always produce one or more new RDDs by applying computations. The result RDD(s) will always be different from the input. According to the computation, the size can be either bigger (in case of a union) or smaller(in case of a filter) or even the same (in case of a map). By applying transformations the user incrementally builds an RDD lineage with all the parent RDDs of the final RDD(s) and they will not be executed before calling an action since transformations are lazy processes. Actions are RDD operations that produce non-RDD values and

³<https://spark.apache.org/>

⁴<https://AMPLAB.cs.berkeley.edu/>

⁵<https://www.apache.org/>

Figure 2.1: R2RML and RML overview. White boxes denote R2RML components, green boxes denote R2RML components extended by RML and orange boxes denote RML specific components. Arrows with white arrowhead denote subclasses, arrows with dashed line and white arrowhead denote the different types of TermMap and simple lines denote associations.

evaluate the RDD(s) lineage graph by triggering the execution of the transformations. Also one of their main purposes is to send the data from Executors to the driver. RDDs are fault tolerant as they track data lineage information to rebuild lost data automatically on failure. Similarly to RDDs, Dataframes and Datasets are immutable collections of data in which the information is organized into named columns, like a table in a relational database. DataFrame allows developers to impose a structure onto a distributed collection of data allowing them to use higher-level functions like SQL operations.

2.5.1 Support of spatial formats

GeoSpark⁶ [JY18] is an in-memory cluster computing framework developed by the Data Systems Lab⁷, in order to support spatial data types, indexes, and processing of large-scale spatial data.

⁶<http://geospark.datasyslab.org/>

⁷<https://www.datasyslab.net/>

GeoSpark consists of three layers: Apache Spark Layer, Spatial RDD Layer and Spatial Query Processing Layer. Apache Spark Layer provides basic Spark functionalities that include loading/storing data to disk as well as regular RDD operations. Spatial RDD Layer consists of three novel Spatial Resilient Distributed Datasets (SRDDs) which extend regular Apache Spark RDDs to support geometrical and spatial objects. GeoSpark provides a geometrical operations library that accesses Spatial RDDs to perform basic geometrical operations (e.g., Overlap, Intersect). System users can leverage the newly defined SRDDs to effectively develop spatial data processing programs in Spark. The Spatial Query Processing Layer efficiently executes spatial query processing algorithms (e.g., Spatial Range, Join, KNN query) on SRDDs. GeoTriples-Spark uses GeoSpark in order to import ESRI Shapefiles.

2.6 Hops

Hops is an open source new distribution of Apache Hadoop developed by KTH, RISE SICS, and Logical Clocks AB. Hops is the main data, cloud and machine learning platform that is used in ExtremeEarth. KTH and LogicalClocks are partners of the project. Its acronym stands for Hadoop Open Platform-as-a-Service and its main feature is that uncorks Hadoop’s metadata bottleneck by introducing a scale-out distributed metadata layer.

The problem of Hadoop that Hops manages to overcome, is that in cases with a more write-intensive workload (20% writes), the throughput drops to 20K filesystem operations/sec rather than the about 80K operations/sec that occur on typical read-heavy industrial workloads. The reason for this is the existence of a global filesystem lock for writes, even though multiple concurrent readers are supported. This global lock also affects negatively the client latency when running at scale. The main source of the problem is the use of a single JVM process as a metadata server, the NameNode. Due to JVM garbage collection artefacts, metadata size is limited to just a few hundred GB, and the lack of support for transactions means that a single global write lock is used to protect metadata from concurrent modification.

Figure 2.2: Hopswork Architecture

2.6.1 HopsFS

The developers of Hops solved this problem by developing HopsFS which is a drop-in replacement of HDFS. In HopsFS, the metadata is stored in an external in-memory distributed database, and multiple stateless NameNodes coordinate the access to metadata. As a result, client latencies for metadata operations are ten times lower in HopsFS compared to HDFS. The work published at

[SNJD] shows some exciting results for HopsFS that enables an order of magnitude larger and higher throughput clusters compared to HDFS.

2.6.2 HopsYARN

HopsYARN is a replacement of YARN that handles metadata in a different way than YARN. While YARN keeps the metadata in-memory on a Java heap, HopsYARN also persists it to the database for recovery. The persisted metadata is used to provide a Quota service for CPU/Memory in Hopsworks.

2.6.3 Hopswork

Hopsworks⁸ [MI] is a data platform that integrates popular platforms for data processing such as Apache Spark, TensorFlow, Hops Hadoop, Kafka, and many others. All services provided by Hopsworks can be accessed using either its REST API or User Interface. Figure 2.2 presents the architecture of Hopswork.

⁸<https://www.hops.site>

3. The Tool GeoTriples

In this section we present the tool GeoTriples that we developed for transforming geospatial data sources into RDF. The material in this section has been taken (sometimes verbatim) from [KK18]. GeoTriples¹ is an open-source tool that is distributed freely according to the Mozilla Public License v2.0. In this section we will present the architecture of GeoTriples and discuss its main components and their respective implementation details. We will then describe how GeoTriples generates R2RML and RML mappings for transforming data that reside in spatially-enabled databases and raw files, and, finally, and how it processes these mappings to produce an RDF graph that follows the GeoSPARQL, stRDF or any other user-defined vocabulary.

3.1 System Architecture

In this section, we present the system architecture of GeoTriples that is depicted in Figure 3.1. The input data for GeoTriples can be geospatial data and metadata stored in ESRI Shapefiles, XML, GML, KML, JSON, GeoJSON and CSV documents or spatially-enabled relational databases (e.g., PostGIS and MonetDB). GeoTriples has a connector that is responsible for providing an abstraction layer that allows the rest of the components to transparently access the input data. GeoTriples comprises three main components: the mapping generator, the mapping processor and the stSPARQL/GeoSPARQL evaluator.

The mapping generator is given as input a data source and creates automatically an R2RML/RML mapping document, depending on the type of the input. The generated mapping is enriched with subject and predicate-object maps, taking into account all transformations that are needed to produce an RDF graph that is compliant with the GeoSPARQL vocabulary. Afterwards, the user may edit the generated mapping document to make it comply with her requirements (e.g., use a different vocabulary). We point out that the ability of GeoTriples to use different vocabularies is a useful feature since even standardized vocabularies such as the one of GeoSPARQL can be dropped, modified or extended in the future.

The mapping processor may use either the generated mapping document or one created by the user from scratch. Based on the triples map definitions in the mapping file, the component generates the final RDF graph which can be manifested in any of the popular RDF syntaxes such as Turtle, RDF/XML, Notation3 or N-Triples. The mapping processor has been implemented in two ways. The first implementation runs on a single processor, while the second runs in a distributed manner using the Apache Spark and Hops framework. The second implementation will be described in detail in Section 4.

The *stSPARQL/GeoSPARQL evaluator* is a component that evaluates an stSPARQL/GeoSPARQL query over a relational database given an R2RML mapping. It supports the evaluation of stSPARQL/GeoSPARQL queries over virtual RDF graphs defined through R2RML mappings to a geospatial relational database.

3.2 Implementation Details

To implement GeoTriples, we chose to extend the D2RQ platform[CBG⁺] which is a well-known system for publishing relational data into RDF. D2RQ provides an interface for generating and processing R2RML mappings for a variety of relational databases that are accessible via JDBC. To

¹<http://geotriples.di.uoa.gr>

Figure 3.1: The system architecture of GeoTriples

support the processing of other data sources, GeoTriples also extends the iMinds RML processor² to process RML mappings of relational databases as well as other data sources. GeoTriples uses the GeoTools³ library for processing geometric objects within ESRI shapefiles, GML, KML, GeoJSON and CSV documents. The GDAL⁴ library is also integrated into the application as an alternative for processing ESRI shapefiles more efficiently.

3.3 Automatic generation of R2RML and RML mappings

GeoTriples can automatically produce an R2RML or RML mapping document that can then be used to generate an RDF graph that corresponds to the input database or file.

Let us first discuss how mappings are generated when the input is a geospatial relational database, a CSV or a shapefile. In these cases, R2RML/RML mappings that are generated by GeoTriples consist of two triples maps: one for handling thematic information and one for handling geospatial information. The triples map that handles non-geometric (thematic) information defines a logical table that contains the attributes of the input data source and a unique identifier for the generated instances. The latter could be either the primary key of the table or a row number of each tuple in the dBase table of a shapefile. Combined with a URI template, the unique identifier is used to produce the URIs that are the subjects of the produced triples. For each column of the input data source, GeoTriples generates an RDF predicate according to the name of the column and a predicate-object map. This map generates predicate-object pairs consisting of the generated predicate and the column values.

The triples map that handles geospatial information defines a logical table with a unique identifier similar to the thematic one. The logical table contains a serialization of the geometric information according to the WKT format, and all attributes of the geometry that are required for producing a GeoSPARQL compliant RDF graph. For this purpose, if the input is a shapefile or a CSV, GeoTriples constructs RML mappings with transformations that invoke GeoSPARQL/stSPARQL extension functions. If the input is a relational database, GeoTriples constructs SQL queries that utilize the appropriate spatial functions of the Open Geospatial Consortium standard "Simple Feature Access - Part 2: SQL Option"⁵ that generate the information required. For example, in order to generate triples that describe the dimensionality of a geometry, GeoTriples creates an

²<http://rml.io/>

³<https://geotools.org/>

⁴<https://gdal.org/>

⁵<https://www.opengeospatial.org/standards/sfs>

RML mapping that invokes the `strdf:dimension` SPARQL extension function that is evaluated over a geometry of a shapefile, or utilizes the PostGIS SQL function `ST_Dimension` when dealing with a spatially-enabled relational database.

A different approach is followed when the input data source is an XML document. In this case, GeoTriples utilizes information from the XML Schema Definition (XSD) language file that describes the structure of the input XML document for generating the appropriate RML mappings. In XML Schema, two kinds of types are defined: simple and complex. Simple types⁶, whether built-in (e.g., `xsd:integer`) or user-defined, are restrictions of the base type definitions (e.g., positive integers with maximum value 122 for representing age information). We define as a simple element an XML element of simple type. By definition, a simple element may contain only text and cannot contain any other XML elements or attributes. A complex type⁷ is a set of attribute declarations and a content type that is applicable to the attributes and children of an element information item respectively. We define a complex element to be an XML element of complex type.

For mapping an XSD document to an ontology, we define a strategy mapping XSD elements and attributes to RDFS classes and properties. We introduce three rules for the generation of an RML mapping and an ontology for any XML schema.

1. Each simple element is mapped to a predicate-object map and an OWL datatype property.
2. Each complex element is mapped to a triples map and an RDFS class.
3. Nested complex elements are mapped to a predicate-object map and an OWL object property.

A well-adopted standard for representing geospatial features in XML is the Geography Markup Language (GML) which has been defined by the Open Geospatial Consortium. We introduce the following rules for handling geometric information that may be present in an input XSD document that follows the GML standard.

1. For every `gml:AbstractGeometryType`, we create a new triples map. All generated IRIs will be instances of the class `ogc:Geometry`.
2. For each newly created triples map, we generate a predicate-object map for each geometric property defined in the geometry extension component of GeoSPARQL. Each predicate-object map must utilize the appropriate GeoSPARQL or stSPARQL extension functions for performing the desired transformation.
3. We generate a property-object map that will create a `ogc:hasGeometry` link between the current triples map and the triples map of the parent XML element.

Besides the data model used by GML and KML documents, there is no other standard practice to represent geospatial information inside XML documents. As a result, a custom approach must be followed by editing the RML mapping accordingly.

3.4 Processing of R2RML and RML Mappings

In this section, we will present in detail the R2RML and RML processor of GeoTriples. The algorithms employed by the processor are 1 and 2 where we highlight with comments our extensions.

⁶https://www.w3.org/TR/xmlschema11-1/#Simple_Type_Definition

⁷https://www.w3.org/TR/xmlschema11-1/#Complex_Type_Definition

In Algorithm 1 we present how GeoTriples processes an R2RML mapping when the input data source is a spatially-enabled relational database. In this case, GeoTriples uses the extended D2RQ mapping processor. The process starts by parsing the input mapping and storing it in memory. For each triples map, the mapping processor performs the following steps. At first, the processor extracts the logical table from the document, constructs the effective SQL query, and stores it in memory. Every logical table has an effective SQL query that, if executed, produces as its result the contents of the logical table. If the subject map is a template-valued term map or a column-valued term map, the related columns are extracted and stored in memory. Then, the processor iterates over all predicate-object maps, and for each one, it extracts all template- and column-valued term maps. These term maps are cached in memory along with the position that they appear on (i.e., whether they are a subject, predicate, object or graph map). Notice that there is no upper bound on the number of predicate or object maps that may appear in a predicate-object map. Afterwards, the processor constructs an SQL query statement that projects all column names that are referenced by the term maps that appear in the subject, predicate and object positions for the current predicate map. The constructed query is posed to the database and then the processor iterates over the results. For each predicate and object value in the result row, a new RDF triple is constructed. If the object map is a referencing object map, a new SQL query is constructed. The SELECT clause will contain the column names that are referenced by the subject map of the parent triples map and the subject and predicate column names of the current predicate-object map. The effective SQL queries of the current triples map and the parent triples map are used as the relations in the FROM clause. The child and parent columns are joined in the WHERE clause of the query. If there are more than one referencing object maps in the same predicate-object map, the WHERE clause will contain multiple equi-joins between the child and parent column names.

For processing RML mappings, the GeoTriples mapping processor extends the RML processor of the tool iMinds. In Algorithm 2 we present how GeoTriples processes an RML mapping. For each triples map, it opens the data source defined in the logical source and poses the defined iterator query to the data source, using the appropriate library. After receiving the result set, the mapping processor iterates through all features in the results, and for each feature, it iterates through all predicate-object maps and processes each one to form the desired RDF triples. For each feature, the processor extracts the values that are referenced by template-valued and reference-valued term maps that appear in the current predicate-object map. In the case of a referencing object map, the processor accesses the logical source of the parent triples map, to get the resulting features. Then, it selects only the features that have equal values on the parent and the child references. For these features, an RDF triple is generated using the result of the parent triples map's subject map as the object RDF term. The same procedure is followed for each referencing object map that may appear in the RML mapping.

Algorithm 1 Processing R2RML mappings

```

1: Data: R2RML Mapping /* The mapping can also contain transformation functions */
2: Result: RDF graph
3: for each triples map in mapping do
4:   Scan logical table;
5:   effectiveQuery ← ConstructEffectiveQuery(logical table);
6:   sColumns ← ExtractColumnNames(subject map);
7:   /* We have extended predicate-object map, in order to support transformation functions */
8:   for each predicate-object map in triples map do
9:     for each predicate map in predicate-object map do
10:      pColumns ← ExtractColumnNames(predicate map);
11:      for each object map do
12:        if ObjectMapType(object map) = referencing object map then
13:          parentTriplesMap ← GetParentTriplesMap(object map);
14:          parentEffectiveQuery ← GetParentEffectiveQuery(parent TriplesMap);
15:          parentTMCColumns ← XtractColNamesFromParentSubject(parent TriplesMap);
16:          childColumn ← GetChildColumn(object map);
17:          parentColumn ← GetParentColumn(object map);
18:          effectiveQuery ← ConstructJointEffectiveQuery(effectiveQuery,
19:            parentEffectiveQuery, childColumn, parentColumn);
20:          projections ← sColumns, pColumns, parentTMCColumns;
21:        else
22:          oColumns ← ExtractColumnNames(object map);
23:          projections ← sColumns, pColumns, oColumns;
24:        end if
25:        resultSet ← PoseQuery(projections, effectiveQuery);
26:        for each result row in resultSet do
27:          /* We have extended the process of the construction of the RDF triples,
28:            in order to produce the results of the transformation functions */
29:          ConstructRDFTriple(result row);
30:        end for
31:      end for
32:    end for
33:  end for
34: end for

```

Algorithm 2 Processing RML mappings

```

1: Data: RML Mapping /* The mapping can also contain transformation functions */
2: Result: RDF graph
3: for each triples map in mapping do
4:   Scan logical source;
5:   iterator ← ExtractIterator(logical source);
6:   ReferenceFormulation ← ExtractReferenceFormulation(logical source);
7:   logicalReferences ← ExtractLogicalReferences(triples map);
8:   subjectMap ← ExtractSubjectMap(triples map);
9:   switch ReferenceFormulation do Select processor implementation
10:    case Xpath Select XML processor;
11:    case JSONPath Select JSON processor;
12:    case SHP Select Shapefile processor;
13:    case SQL Select SQL processor;
14:    default Error(Wrong input)
15:   /* The iterator is an SQL query which projects all logical references */
16:   iterator ← ConstructNewSQLIterator(logicalReferences, iterator);
17: endsw
18: resultSet ← ExecuteIterator(iterator);
19: for each result row in resultSet do
20:   sValues ← ExtractSubjectValues(SubjectMap, result row);
21:   /* We have extended predicate-object map, in order to support transformation functions */
22:   for each predicate-object map do
23:     for each predicate map do
24:       pValues ← ExtractPredicateValues(predicate map, result row);
25:       for each object map do
26:         if ObjectMapType(object map) = referencing object map then
27:           parentTriplesMap ← GetParentTriplesMap(object map);
28:           parentSubjectMap ← ExtractSubjectMap(parentTriplesMap);
29:           childColumn ← GetChildReference(object map);
30:           childValue ← ExtractChildValue(object map, result row);
31:           parentColumn ← GetParentReference(object map);
32:           parentResultSet ← ExtractResultSet(parentTriplesMap);
33:           for each p result row in parentResultSet do
34:             sParentValues ← ExtractSubjectValues(parentSubjectMap, result row);
35:             parentValue ← ExtractParentValue(object map, result row);
36:             if childValue = parentValue then
37:               /* We have extended the process of the construction of the RDF triples,
38:                in order to produce the results of the transformation functions */
39:               ConstructRDFTriple(sValues, pValues, sParentValues);
40:             end if
41:           end for
42:         else
43:           oValues ← ExtractObjectValues(object map, result row);
44:           /* Our extension takes place here as well */
45:           ConstructRDFTriple(sValues, pValues, oValues);
46:         end if
47:       end for
48:     end for
49:   end for
50: end for
51: end for

```

4. Transformation of Big Geospatial Data

In this section we present a new implementation of GeoTriples, capable of transforming big geospatial data into RDF which we call GeoTriples-Spark. To enable the transformation of big geospatial data we extended GeoTriples to run on top of Hops and Apache Spark. This implementation can run in a standalone machine or in a Hadoop based cluster, like Hops. For the transformation, we developed a new processor which is based on the RML processor and it is able to convert data loaded into a Spark Dataset. Currently GeoTriples-Spark supports the distributed transformation of CSV files, ESRI Shapefiles and GeoJSONs.

4.1 Description

The application starts with the *SparkMaster*, which is responsible for all the Spark related actions. Firstly it loads the input data into a Spark Dataset which is a distributed collection of data organized in named columns. Then, it inserts a new column containing unique numbers which will represent the identifiers (IDs) of the rows. Combined with a URI template, the unique identifiers are used to produce the URIs which will be the subjects of the produced triples. This ID column contains monotonically increasing and unique numbers but not necessarily consecutive, as that would require to have counted the rows of the Dataset, which is an expensive action. Then, it executes the processor which converts each record of the Dataset into a collection of RDF triples. The produced RDF triples follow the N-Triples RDF syntax. In the end *SparkMaster* stores the generated triples in the filesystem into multiple files.

In Algorithm 3 we present how the new RML processor functions. It takes as input either a partition of the Dataset and then iterates over its rows or a single row and it converts it into RDF triples. The processor processes the term maps similarly with the RML processor, but in the beginning it processes the input mappings in order to construct ancillary structures which speed up the transformation. As a result, it is faster than the regular RML processor as repetitive actions such as the construction of the predicates and the calculations of the templates are performed once. However, in the current version, this processor does not support referencing objects as it is not yet implemented.

The primary purpose of this implementation is to be capable of converting datasets of enormous sizes into RDF graphs. Hence, it is of major importance to mention that the produced triples significantly exceed the size of the input source, as the N-TRIPLES syntax requires the triples to be written in full. As a result, we had to be very cautious not only with the execution cost of the transformation process but also with memory management in order to avoid running out of memory. So, we have developed two modes for this implementation. The first one is known as "PER PARTITION CONVERSION", and it is implemented using a *mapPartitions* Spark transformation. In this mode, the processor is initialized inside the *mapPartitions* and it transforms all the records of the partition into RDF triples. Then, after the completion of the transformation, the triples are stored in the files via the *saveAsTextFile* Spark action. However, during the execution of *mapPartitions*, the produced triples are stored in memory and remain there till the conversion of the whole partition is completed. As a result, this can significantly slow down the process as the Garbage Collector of Java will be triggered more often and in the worst case scenario if the memory is not sufficient enough it can lead to out of memory errors. The second mode is known as "PER ROW CONVERSION" and it is implemented using a *map* Spark transformation. In this mode, the *map* calls the processor to transform a single row into RDF triples. Then the produced triples of the record are directly written to the corresponding file via the *saveAsTextFile* Spark action. Therefore, the produced triples can be removed from the memory after they are stored in the files, avoiding running out of memory. However, the processor is not a serializable object and hence it requires to reconstruct a copy of it inside the *map* transformation which means to reconstruct it

Algorithm 3 Spark RML processor

```

1: Data: RML Mapping /* The mapping can also contain transformation functions */
2: Data: Dataset /* collection of data organized in named columns */
3: Result: RDF graph
4: predicateList ← {}
5: for each triples map in mapping do
6:   subjectMap ← ExtractSubjectMap(triples map);
7:   sTemplate ← CreateSubjectTemplate(SubjectMap)
8:   for each predicate-object map do
9:     for each predicate map do
10:      pValues ← ExtractPredicateValues(predicate map);
11:      predicateList insert pValue;
12:     end for
13:   end for
14: end for
15: for each row in partition do
16:   sValues ← CreateSubject(sTemplate, row);
17:   for each predicate-object map do
18:     for each predicate map do
19:       pValues ← getPredicate(predicateList, predicate map);
20:       for each object map do
21:         oValues ← ExtractObjectValues(object map, row);
22:         ConstructRDFTriple(sValues, pValues, oValues);
23:       end for
24:     end for
25:   end for
26: end for

```

for each row. This does not have a major impact to the execution as the construction of a copy of the processor is a very fast procedure. We have set this mode as the default mode as it is safer when we are not aware of the required memory of the transformation.

The parallelization of the process is based on the fact that Spark does not load the input data as a whole, but as multiple partitions distributed across the cluster. For each partition, Spark spawns a Task which target is to transform the partition into RDF triples and to store them in a file. Hence, for each partition, a file will be generated containing the records of partition as triples. These files can be easily concatenated since integration is a simple process for data that follows the RDF model. The transformation of each partition can be performed individually from the others because the chunks of the data held in partitions contain independent records that GeoTriples will convert and store in a separate file. As a result, the execution of each partition does not affect the execution of the rest and there is no need for data shuffling or inner communication during the whole process. More partitions mean the more parallelized the whole procedure can be. Moreover, more partitions also mean that each Task will have to transform a smaller chunk of data as the initial dataset will have been divided into more partitions of fewer records. The number of partitions is determined by the file format of the source, its size and the configuration settings of the filesystem.

Furthermore, the parallelization of the process is determined by how many Tasks can run concurrently. These Tasks run inside an Executor (JVM process), in which multiple Tasks run at the same time. The number of Executors and the number of the concurrently executed Tasks are defined by the configurations of Spark and by the available resources of the cluster.

As it was mentioned above, GeoTriples-Spark currently supports the transformation of CSV, GeoJSON and ESRI Shapefiles. CSV files and GeoJSONs are considered text files and hence can be easily loaded into multiple partitions by the API of Spark as they are distributedly stored across

the filesystem. The geometry feature in CSV files is expected to be in Well Known Text (WKT) and therefore it does not require any further pre-processing. Regarding GeoJSON, the application loads the FeatureCollection into a Spark Dataset and constructs a new column containing the geometries as WKT. The case of ESRI shapefiles is a bit more complicated. For loading the input shapefile into a Spark dataset we use the GeoSpark library because the interface of Spark does not contain the necessary parsers. However, GeoSpark always loads the input shapefile into one partition as it merges all the related component files of shapefile into one. This is happening because all the related component files must be located in the same datanode to utilize the shapefile index and the related attributes. Loading shapefiles from a distributed filesystem is a well-known problem and it has been studied extensively in [JA16]. GeoMesa [HR15] manages to overcome this issue by having the shapefile stored in Accumulo or in its specially designed FileSystem. The fact that the input shapefile is loaded into a single partition, forces us to re-partition in order to distribute the loaded Spark Dataset across the cluster and to increase the parallelization of the conversion. Consequently, this significantly increases the execution cost because re-partitioning is a very time-consuming action as it requires data shuffling which signals object serialization, Disk I/O and Network I/O. Therefore, a better approach is to have the shapefile split into multiple shapefiles of smaller sizes and use them as input to the application. As a result, they will be loaded into multiple partitions avoiding the need to re-partition.

4.2 Evaluation

The application was evaluated against multiple files of various sizes. The initial datasets were provided by the download server of GEOFABRIK¹ which contains extracts from the OpenStreetMap project. In order to create datasets of specific sizes, we replicated the initial dataset and constructed datasets of 1GB, 10GB, 100GB and 250GB. Furthermore, in order to increase the input size of the application, these datasets were loaded multiple times. In the end, we evaluated GeoTriples-Spark against input of 1GB, 10GB, 100GB, 250GB, 500GB, 1TB and 2TB. All the test were performed using the "PER ROW CONVERSION" mode of the application as it performs better than the "PER PARTITION CONVERSION" mode. The displayed times are the median values calculated after executing each test five times.

The tests were performed in the Hopswork data platform which contains approximately 1000 CPU cores of 2.40GHz, 12TB of RAM and 1PB of storage. It is undeniable that Hopswork is very powerful cluster enabling us to perform tests at extreme scales. However Hopswork is used by multiple clients and collaborators of Logical Clock AB, and therefore we can not possibly know if there were interferences from external processes that had negative impact to the performance of our application.

4.2.1 CSV

The transformation of CSV is the simplest case as the data are stored distributedly across the cluster and there is no need for data pre-processing. The dataset we used for the evaluation contains information about the road system of Germany provided by the GEOFABRIK download server. It is a wide dataset as it contains 10 columns. By editing and replicating the initial dataset we constructed datasets of 1GB, 10GB, 100GB and 250GB. The numbers of the records and the produced triples of these datasets are depicted in Table 4.1. Then in order to increase the size of the input data, we loaded these datasets multiples times. In all of the tests we used 4 CPU cores and 15GB memory for each Executor

Table 4.2 displays information regarding the tests such as the number of Executors that were used in each test and the size of the output files. Figure 4.1 depicts the performance of the GeoTriples-Spark for CSV documents of diverse sizes. The execution time includes the time it required to load

¹<http://download.geofabrik.de/>

<i>Dataset</i>	<i>Size</i>	<i>#Records</i>	<i>#Produced Triples</i>
1GB.csv	1GB	5607533	58245902
10GB.csv	10GB	52075320	540935480
100GB.csv	100GB	520753200	5409354800
250GB.csv	250GB	1301883000	13523387000

Table 4.1: CSV Datasets

the input, to transform it into RDF triples and to write the results in files. Spark also requires a little time to read the schema of the input which is also included in the execution time. In the case of CSV, this time is neglectable as it is constant for all the datasets and it is approximately 7 seconds.

<i>Dataset</i>	<i>Times</i>	<i>Input Size</i>	<i>#Executors</i>	<i>Output Size</i>	<i>#Execution Time(m)</i>
1GB.csv	1	1GB	2	7.7GB	1
10GB.csv	1	10GB	4	83.4GB	1.1
100GB.csv	1	100GB	41	840.1GB	3.3
250GB.csv	1	250GB	60	2.1TB	6.6
250GB.csv	2	500GB	65	4.1TB	13
250GB.csv	4	1TB	70	8.3TB	26
250GB.csv	8	2TB	80	16.6TB	50

Table 4.2: CSV Tests

Transformation of CSV files

Figure 4.1: Performance of GeoTriples-Spark for CSV datasets of different sizes

We can observe that the escalation of the transformation time over the input size is almost linear without linearly increasing the number of the Executors. As a result, we can deduce that the application is capable of transforming data of extreme scale in a reasonable amount of time without the need for an excessive amount of resources. For instance, it required 50 minutes to transform 2TB of input into 16TB of RDF triples, using 80 Executors of 4 cores each. The 2TB was loaded into 16025 partitions and the application was executing 320 (Executors * cores) Tasks concurrently.

Furthermore, it is important to mention that the application spends most of its time performing I/O. Figure 4.2a and Figure 4.2b shows the frequency of reads and writes in HDFS during the execution of the application. As a result, there is a lot of Disk latency which significantly affects the performance of the application. This is the reason why we only used a fraction of the avail-

able resources of Hopswork as more Executors were leading to an increased Disk I/O traffic. By experimenting with more Executors we observed that even though more Tasks were running concurrently, the latency in Disk increased and as a result it increased the execution time of the overall application as well. We concluded to these numbers of Executors after a lot of experimentation and research.

(a) HDFS bytes reads/s, 10s avgs

(b) HDFS bytes writes/s, 10s avgs

Figure 4.2: HDFS I/O triggered by GeoTriples-Spark during the transformation of 2TB CSV data

4.2.2 GeoJSON

The case of GeoJSON is quite similar to the case of CSV. The input data are directly loaded into multiple partitions and read using the API of Spark. However, spark needs more time to read the schema of the input documents. Furthermore, the transformation of GeoJSON requires a further pre-process to convert the geometries of the FeatureCollections (geometry type and coordinates) into WKT. The construction of the input datasets is similar to the case of CSV and the data contains information about the road system of Australia. The number of the records and the produced triples of each dataset are depicted in Table 4.3.

Table 4.4 contains information about the tests and Figure 4.3 displays the performance of the transformation of GeoJSON files. In all of the tests we used 4 CPU cores and 15GB memory for

<i>Dataset</i>	<i>Size</i>	<i>#Records</i>	<i>#Produced Triples</i>
1GB.geojson	1GB	1550225	16550154
10GB.geojson	10GB	15400348	164414230
100GB.geojson	100GB	153701731	1640921626
250GB.geojson	250GB	383004024	4088955942

Table 4.3: GeoJSON Datasets

<i>Dataset</i>	<i>Times</i>	<i>Input Size</i>	<i>#Executors</i>	<i>Output Size</i>	<i>#Execution Time(m)</i>
1GB.geojson	1	1GB	2	2.6GB	0.67
10GB.geojson	1	10GB	21	26GB	1.51
100GB.geojson	1	100GB	41	261GB	2.64
250GB.geojson	1	250GB	60	654GB	5.1
250GB.geojson	2	500GB	65	1.3TB	8.3
250GB.geojson	4	1TB	70	2.6TB	15.4
250GB.geojson	8	2TB	80	5.2TB	28.3

Table 4.4: GeoJSON Tests

each Executor. The blue line in Figure 4.3 indicates the time used to read the schema of the input and the red one shows the performance of the total execution (including the reading time). We can observe that even though the execution requires more time to read the schema and some additional time for processing the geometries, it performs better than the transformation of CSV. This is due to the fact that GeoJSON files contain significantly fewer records in comparison with the CSV documents of the same size. As a result, it needs significantly less time for the transformation and writing as fewer triples will be generated.

Figure 4.3: Performance of GeoTriples-Spark for GeoJSON datasets of different sizes

4.2.3 ESRI Shapefile

The case of ESRI shapefiles is the most complicated one. As it was mentioned before, the shapefiles are read using the GeoSpark library which always loads each shapefile into a single partition, regardless of its size. User can instruct GeoTriples-Spark to re-partition the loaded data which will re-distribute it into multiple partitions of smaller sizes to all the Executors. We strongly discourage

to use this method as it requires to shuffle data across the cluster and hence it significantly increases the execution time of the application.

Regarding the evaluation of the transformation of shapefiles, we used shapefiles of diverse sizes which we loaded them multiple times in order to increase the size of the input geospatial data. Table 4.5 and Table 4.6 contains information about the input shapefiles which were downloaded from GEOFABRIK.

<i>Dataset</i>	<i>.shp size</i>	<i>.dbf size</i>	<i>Total size</i>
POIs_AUS	3.9MB	19.7MB	24.7 MB
RoadSystem_AUS	381.1MB	278.9MB	672.4 MB
RoadSystem_GER	1.7GB	1.9GB	3.7 GB

Table 4.5: ESRI Shapefiles Datasets

<i>Dataset</i>	<i>#Records</i>	<i>#Produced Triples</i>
POIs_AUS	144600	799924
RoadSystem_AUS	1615868	17165376
RoadSystem_GER	11107532	115146843

Table 4.6: ESRI Shapefiles Datasets

There is a 2 GB size limit for any shapefile component file, which translates to a maximum of roughly 70 million point features. Therefore GeoTriples-Spark provides the option to load multiple shapefiles and transform them at once. User can specify as input a folder that contains multiple folders of shapefiles. Then, GeoTriples-Spark will load each shapefile into a single Spark Dataset and in the end it will unite all of them into one. This process is performed serially and therefore the number of the folders affects the execution time. Furthermore, each shapefile will be read into a single partition and it will be transformed individually into RDF triples. As a result, the sizes of the input shapefiles also impacts the performance of the application. If a few big shapefiles are given as input, then GeoTriples-Spark will require less time to read them but they will be loaded into few partitions of many records and therefore each Task will require more time. On the other hand, by loading more small shapefiles will result in an increased reading time but each Task will be performed faster as each partition will contain fewer records.

This can be comprehended by the tests presented in Table 4.7 and Figure 4.4. In these tests we executed GeoTriples-Spark by loading POIs_AUS and RoadSystem_AUS multiple times till the input size reach a targeted value. For each execution we used 3 Executors with 10 CPU cores and 15GB of memory each. By comparing their performance we can deduce that even though the execution of multiple small shapefiles can be more parallelized, the cost of reading them is significantly high. Furthermore, when we loaded the RoadSystem_AUS two times, the data were loaded into two partitions and therefore two Tasks were spawned. As a result, only one Executor and two of its cores were utilized which led to this bad performance. However in the case when we load it 15 times, the execution was more parallelized and the performance was noticeably better.

<i>Dataset</i>	<i>Times</i>	<i>Input Size</i>	<i>Output Size</i>	<i>Reading T. (s)</i>	<i>Transformation T. (s)</i>
POIs_AUS	53	1.3GB	6.8GB	47	23
RoadSystem_AUS	2	1.3GB	5.5GB	14	119
POIs_AUS	408	9.8GB	52.7GB	128	108
RoadSystem_AUS	15	9.8GB	41,6GB	25	120

Table 4.7: Performance of GeoTriples-Spark for reading multiple ESRI Shapefiles

Table 4.8 and Figure 4.5 depict the performance of GeoTripls-Spark against big geospatial data loaded by multiple shapefiles. The reason that the transformation of shapefiles is slower than the rest, is because of some peculiarities of Hopswork. Hopswork contains some worker that are not

Figure 4.4: Performance of GeoTriples-Spark for reading multiple ESRI Shapefiles

<i>Dataset</i>	<i>Times</i>	<i>Input Size</i>	<i>#Executors</i>	<i>#Cores</i>	<i>Output Size</i>	<i>Execution Time (m)</i>
RoadSystem_AUS	2	1.3GB	1	2	5.5 GB	1.2
RoadSystem_AUS	15	9.8GB	3	5	41.6 GB	2.5
RoadSystem_AUS	153	100.5 GB	20	8	427.7 GB	4.3
RoadSystem_AUS	381	250.2 GB	30	10	1068.6 GB	9.9
RoadSystem_GER	136	502.9 GB	15	10	2.5 TB	17
RoadSystem_GER	258	1TB	27	10	5.1 TB	34

Table 4.8: ESRI Shapefile Tests

Transformation of ESRI Shapefiles

Figure 4.5: Performance of GeoTriples-Spark against Shapefile datasets

datanodes and therefore they do not contain locally the data their Executors need to process. Therefore their Executors perform network I/O in order to read and write the data to the closest datanode. This was also observed to the previous cases, but they did not affect the performance as these Executors were applied with fewer Tasks than the rest and they managed to complete them before the Executors with more workload. However, in the transformation of shapefiles each Task

performs the conversion of a whole shapefile and all the Task are performed simultaneously. We managed to reduce the problem by using Spark’s configuration for speculative execution of Tasks. This is a health-check procedure that checks for Tasks to be speculated, i.e. running slower in a stage than the median of all successfully completed Tasks in a taskset. Such slow Tasks will be re-submitted to another worker. It does not stop the slow Tasks, but run a new copy in parallel. For instance, in the transformation of 1TB, all Tasks have been completed before the 20th minute except for those that are executed in these worker . After the 20th minute only these slow Tasks and the re-submitted ones are running. This can be observed by the Figure 4.6a and Figure 4.6b which display the frequency of reads and writes in the HDFS in the case of 1TB input. Fortunately, after the next upgrade of Hopswork will probably support node labelling which will enable us to restrict these worker from receiving Tasks. We believe that the transformation of 1TB of ESRI Shapefiles without using these worker, will require approximately 20 minutes.

(a) HDFS bytes reads/s, 10s avgs

(b) HDFS bytes writes/s, 10s avgs

Figure 4.6: HDFS I/O triggered by GeoTriples-Spark during the transformation of 1TB of geospatial data loaded by ESRI Shapefiles

4.2.4 Execution in HDFS

Figure 4.7 displays the performance of GeoTriples-Spark in a single-node pseudo-distributed cluster. The cluster contains 32 CPU cores of 3.3GHz and 126GB of memory. In all the experiments we

Figure 4.7: Execution of GeoTriples-Spark in a pseudo-distributed HDFS cluster

used 8 Executors with 4 cores each, which means that all the available CPU cores were running concurrently executing Tasks. However, it is important to mention that all the Executors were running in the same datanode and thus they were performing I/O in the same Disk. That led to an increased Disk I/O latency and therefore the CPU cores were forced to under-perform (the utilization of each CPU core was around 20% instead of 100%). The depicted executions in Hops were performed using 8 Executors with 4 CPU cores(2.4GHz) each as well. In these executions, each Executor was running in a different datanode and therefore, the Disk I/O of each Executor was not affecting the Disk I/O of the rest. We decided to depict the performances of GeoTriples-Spark in Hops in order to work as ground truth, and not in order to compare them. Taking into account the significant differences between these two environment, we reckon that the comparison of the executions in Hops and in this single-node cluster would not have been sensible.

5. Summary

In this deliverable we present the transformation of big geospatial data into linked open data. The transformation will be implemented using GeoTriples-Spark. In this deliverable we presented the tool GeoTriples and its extension GeoTriples-Spark that runs on top of Hops and Apache Spark. The current version supports the parallel transformation of ESRI Shapefiles, CSV and GeoJSON files into RDF triples that follow the N-TRIPLE syntax. The evaluation of GeoTriples-Spark was performed in the Hopswork data platform which is a very powerful cluster. Using just a small fraction of Hopswork resources, GeoTriples-Spark manages to transform terabytes of geospatial data in less than an hour.

Bibliography

- [ALH09] Sren Auer, Jens Lehmann, and Sebastian Hellmann. LinkedGeoData: Adding a Spatial Dimension to the Web of Data. In Abraham Bernstein, David R. Karger, Tom Heath, Lee Feigenbaum, Diana Maynard, Enrico Motta, and Krishnaprasad Thirunarayan, editors, *The Semantic Web - ISWC 2009*, volume 5823 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 731–746. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2009.
- [BAPS12] Alexandre Bertails, Marcelo Arenas, Eric Prud’hommeaux, and Juan Sequeda. A Direct Mapping of Relational Data to RDF. W3C Recommendation, 2012. Available from: <http://www.w3.org/TR/rdb-direct-mapping/>.
- [BL] Tim Berners-Lee. Relational Databases on the Semantic Web. <http://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/RDB-RDF.html>.
- [BSK13] Konstantina Bereta, Panayiotis Smeros, and Manolis Koubarakis. Representation and querying of valid time of triples in linked geospatial data. In Philipp Cimiano, Oscar Corcho, Valentina Presutti, Laura Hollink, and Sebastian Rudolph, editors, *The Semantic Web: Semantics and Big Data*, volume 7882 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 259–274. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2013.
- [CBG⁺] Richard Cyganiak, Chris Bizer, Jirg Garbers, Oliver Maresch, and Christian Becker. The D2RQ Platform. Available from: <http://d2rq.org/>.
- [CV13] Kevin Chentout and Alejandro A. Vaisman. Adding Spatial Support to R2RML Mappings. In *OTM Workshops*, volume 8186 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*. Springer, 2013.
- [DKF⁺15] Anastasia Dimou, Dimitris Kontokostas, Markus Freudenberg, Ruben Verborgh, Jens Lehmann, Erik Mannens, Sebastian Hellmann, and Rik Van de Walle. Assessing and Refining Mappings to RDF to Improve Dataset Quality. In *The Semantic Web - ISWC 2015 - 14th International Semantic Web Conference, Bethlehem, PA, USA, October 11-15, 2015, Proceedings, Part II*, pages 133–149, 2015.
- [dLSV⁺10] Alexander de Len, Victor Saquicela, Luis M. Vilches, Boris Villazn-Terrazas, Freddy Priyatna, and Oscar Corcho. Geographical linked data: A Spanish use case. In *Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Semantic Systems, I-SEMANTICS ’10*, pages 36:1–36:3, New York, NY, USA, 2010. ACM.
- [DSC12] Souripriya Das, Seema Sundara, and Richard Cyganiak. R2RML: RDB to RDF Mapping Language. W3C Recommendation, 2012. Available from: <http://www.w3.org/TR/r2rml/>.
- [DVSC⁺14] Anastasia Dimou, Miel Vander Sande, Pieter Colpaert, Ruben Verborgh, Erik Mannens, and Rik Van de Walle. RML: A generic language for integrated RDF mappings of heterogeneous data. In *Proceedings of the 7th Workshop on Linked Data on the Web*, April 2014.
- [geo12] Open Geospatial Consortium. GeoSPARQL - A geographic query language for RDF data. OpenGIS Implementation Standard, November 2012. Available from: https://portal.opengeospatial.org/files/?artifact_id=47664.
- [HR15] Eichelberger Hughes, Annex and Ronquest. GeoMesa: a distributed architecture for spatio-temporal fusion, 2015.
- [JA16] M. B. Potdar Jhummarwala Abdul, Mazin Alkathiri. Geospatial Hadoop (GS-Hadoop) an efficient mapreduce based engine for distributed processing of shapefiles, 2016. Available from: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7748956>.

- [JY18] Mohamed Sarwat Jia Yu, Zongsi Zhang. Spatial Data Management in Apache Spark: The GeoSpark Perspective and Beyond, 2018. Available from: http://www.public.asu.edu/~jiayu2/geospark/publication/GeoSpark_Geoinformatica_2018.pdf.
- [KBP⁺17] Manolis Koubarakis, Konstantina Bereta, George Papadakis, Dimitrianos Savva, and George Stamoulis. Big, linked geospatial data and its applications in Earth observation. *IEEE Internet Computing*, 21(4):87–91, 2017.
- [KK18] Ioannis Vlachopoulos Alexandros Vasileiou Nikolaos Karalis Manolis Koubarakis Stefan Manegold Kostis Kyzirakosa, Dimitrianos Savva. GeoTriples: Transforming Geospatial Data into RDF Graphs Using R2RML and RML Mappings. *Journal of Web Semantics*, 2018. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1570826818300428>.
- [KKG⁺14] Kostis Kyzirakos, Manos Karpathiotakis, George Garbis, Charalampos Nikolaou, Konstantina Bereta, Ioannis Papoutsis, Themis Herekakis, Dimitrios Michail, Manolis Koubarakis, and Charalambos Kontoes. Wildfire monitoring using satellite images, ontologies and linked geospatial data. *Journal of Web Semantics*, 24:18–26, 2014.
- [KKK⁺12a] M. Koubarakis, M. Karpathiotakis, K. Kyzirakos, C. Nikolaou, and M. Sioutis. Data models and query languages for linked geospatial data. In *Invited tutorial at the 8th Reasoning Web Summer School 2012 (RW 2012)*. In: Eiter, T., Krennwallner, T. (eds.) *Reasoning Web. Semantic Technologies for Advanced Query Answering. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol. 7487, pp. 290–328. Springer., 2012.
- [KKK12b] Kostis Kyzirakos, Manos Karpathiotakis, and Manolis Koubarakis. Strabon: A semantic geospatial DBMS. In Philippe Cudré-Mauroux, Jeff Heflin, Evren Sirin, Tania Tudorache, Jérôme Euzenat, Manfred Hauswirth, Josiane Xavier Parreira, Jim Hendler, Guus Schreiber, Abraham Bernstein, and Eva Blomqvist, editors, *International Semantic Web Conference (1)*, volume 7649 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 295–311. Springer, 2012.
- [MI] Theofilos Kakantousis Gautier Berthou Jim Dowling. Mahmoud Ismail, Ermias Gebremeskel. Hopsworks: Improving User Experience and Development on Hadoop with Scalable, Strongly Consistent Metadata,.
- [MZ10] Michael J. Franklin Scott Shenker Ion Stoica Matei Zaharia, Mosharaf Chowdhury. Spark: Cluster Computing with Working Sets, 2010. Available from: http://people.csail.mit.edu/matei/papers/2010/hotcloud_spark.pdf.
- [MZ12] Tathagata Das Ankur Dave Justin Ma Murphy McCauley Michael J. Franklin Scott Shenker Ion Stoica Matei Zaharia, Mosharaf Chowdhury. Resilient Distributed Datasets: A Fault-Tolerant Abstraction for In-Memory Cluster Computing, 2012. Available from: http://people.csail.mit.edu/matei/papers/2012/nsdi_spark.pdf.
- [PAGA14] Kostas Patroumpas, Michalis Alexakis, Giorgos Giannopoulos, and Spiros Athanasiou. TripleGeo: an ETL Tool for Transforming Geospatial Data into RDF Triples. In *Proceedings of the Workshops of the EDBT/ICDT 2014 Joint Conference (EDBT/ICDT 2014)*, volume 1133 of *CEUR Workshop Proceedings*. CEUR-WS.org, 2014.
- [SNJD] Seif Haridi Salman Niazi, Mahmoud Ismail and Spotify AB; Mikael Ronstråm Oracle Jim Dowling, KTH Royal Institute of Technology; Steffen Grohsschmiedt. HopsFS: Scaling Hierarchical File System Metadata Using NewSQL Databases. Available from: <https://www.usenix.org/conference/fast17/technical-sessions/presentation/niazi>.
- [Ste06] Damian Steer. SquirrelRDF, 2006. Available from: <https://sourceforge.net/projects/jena/files/Archive/SquirrelRDF/>.